

Kseniya A. MALTSEVA

Vladivostok State University of Economics and Service (Vladivostok, Primorsky Krai, Russia)
email: maltseva_ksenechka@outlook.com; ORCID: 0000-0003-4146-869X

Artem Yu. KONONOV

Vladivostok State University of Economics and Service (Vladivostok, Primorsky Krai, Russia)
PhD in Economics; e-mail: artem.kononov@yahoo.com; ORCID: 0000-0003-1955-0910

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MILITARY HERITAGE TOURISM IN PRIMORSKY KRAI (CASE OF THE VLADIVOSTOK FORTRESS)

Abstract. *The article analyzes the problems and prospects for the development of military heritage tourism with the evidence from Primorsky Krai. The study notes the significance of military heritage tourism in Russia, due to the rich historical heritage the country possesses. There is general trend for restoration, as well as for adaptation of military heritage sites for tourist purposes. Former fortress complexes, memorials, other structures are being restored, museumified, used as popular tourist sites. Similarly, the number of relevant festivals, events is growing. At the same time, the analysis shows that in relation to these realities, Primorsky Krai can be recognized as the region that has the necessary resources and opportunities for the further development of military heritage programs. The dominant resource is the Vladivostok Fortress, tourist potential of which is just beginning to develop, however, it already allows using various methods, forms of creating a tourist product. Thematic events, exhibitions, excursions, covering not only the ground part of the fortification, but underground components as well are developing today, taking advantage of demand from the local population and foreign tourists. At the same time, during the analysis, certain problems were also identified, and the ways to solve them were proposed.*

Keywords: *military heritage tourism, fortification, Vladivostok fortress, historical heritage, Primorsky Krai, regional tourist product*

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МАЛЬЦЕВА Ксения Андреевна

*Владивостокский государственный университет экономики и сервиса
(Владивосток, Приморский край, РФ)
e-mail: maltseva_ksenechka@outlook.com; ORCID: 0000-0003-4146-869X*

КОНОНОВ Артем Юрьевич

*Владивостокский государственный университет экономики и сервиса
(Владивосток, Приморский край, РФ)
кандидат экономических наук; e-mail: artem.kononov@yahoo.com; ORCID: 0000-0003-1955-0910*

ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ВОЕННО-ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В ПРИМОРСКОМ КРАЕ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ВЛАДИВОСТОКСКОЙ КРЕПОСТИ)

В статье анализируются проблемы и перспективы развития военно-исторического туризма на примере Приморского края. В ходе исследования отмечается актуальность военно-исторического туризма в Российской Федерации, обусловленная богатым историческим наследием страны. Фиксируется общий тренд на восстановление, а также адаптацию использования объектов военного наследия в туристических целях. Бывшие комплексы крепостей, различные мемориалы, иные сооружения реставрируются, музефицируются и используются в качестве популярных туристических объектов. Аналогично растёт количество соответствующих фестивалей и мероприятий. При этом проведенный анализ показывает, что в отношении этих реалий Приморский край можно признать тем субъектом, что имеет все необходимые ресурсы и возможности для дальнейшего развития военно-исторических программ. В данном случае главным ресурсом выступает Владивостокская крепость, чей туристский потенциал только начинает стремительно развиваться, однако уже, несомненно, позволяет использовать различные методы, формы и способы создания туристского продукта. Тематические мероприятия, выставки, экскурсии, охватывающие не только наземную часть фортификации, но и подземные составляющие в том числе, сегодняшним днём развиваются достаточно успешно, пользуясь спросом как у местного населения, так и у иностранных туристов. При этом в ходе проведенного анализа также выявлены определенные проблемы, которые сдерживают развитие военно-исторического туризма в Приморском крае, и вместе с тем предложены пути их решения.

Ключевые слова: *военно-исторический туризм, фортификация, Владивостокская крепость, историческое наследие, Приморский край, региональный туристский продукт*

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Introduction

At the present time the uprising interest of citizens to military history is undeniable, because a continuous process, which determines the motivation to study state history, also contributes to the establishment of a sense of spiritual unity and respect for the foretime of our country. This leads to the fact that military heritage tourism is deemed an important direction of state policy in tourism.

Back in 2013, the former head of Federal Agency for Tourism (Rostourism) Alexander Radkov emphasized the importance of this phenomenon, stating that "one of the main appeals for foreign tourists to come to us is the desire to learn something from our spiritual heritage, <... >. In this regard the subject of military heritage tourism is not incidental as Russia sure has heroic past"¹.

At the same time, in the domestic market the relevance of military heritage tourism was already highlighted in the Federal Target Program "Development of domestic and inbound tourism in the Russian Federation (2011-2018)", which outlined the fact that the historical and cultural heritage is the most important competitive advantage of a destination. According to the text of the Program: "Development of tourist infrastructure, <... > along with the introduction of restored historical and cultural heritage sites to the general public, will create conditions for the development of a number of new tourist routes of various directions. This will satisfy consumer demand <...> and ensure a steady growth of the tourist inflow". However, the text of the Program also noted that trips with cultural and educational purposes already account for "about 20% of the domestic tourist flow"².

At the same time, work on the restoration and museumization of former fortress complexes, memorials, and other structures does not stop;

the number of relevant festivals and events is growing. An intermediate result of such trends can be the example of the Kulikovo cluster, which was established in September 2021 and which will unite the tourist resources of Tula region around the "Kulikovo Field" museum-reserve.

In this regard, there is an opportunity to validate military heritage tourism as a priority direction of the tourism industry in the country and to point out the prospects for its successful development both at the federal and regional levels.

Literature review

Military heritage tourism is a complex phenomenon. Given the flow of the World history, military heritage tourism receives significant attention of scholars all across the globe.

A. Elliott and D. Milne showcase the example of developing military heritage tourism in Japan. Research suggests that tourism can become a well-needed peaceful and anti-militarist practice that can play an important role, not only in international diplomacy, but also as a transmission tool for memories of war to current and future generations [1].

S. Driessen, M. Grever and S. Reijnders examine the psychological aspect of military heritage tourism in Netherlands to verify that that such tours help to evoke a specific placebound engagement with the past [2].

D. Foulk outlines that military heritage tourism in France, while being the niche market, has encouraged the reinvention of certain areas of the country that were prime examples of deindustrialisation. This has allowed them to capitalize upon their historic past and for tourism to flourish [3].

The study by A. Zienkiewicz, T. Podciborski, R. Kaźmierczak explore the examples of military heritage sites in northern and north-eastern Poland to confirm that military tourism is indeed a rapidly growing segment of the national tourist

¹ Rosturizm will promote military-historical routes. URL: <https://tass.ru/obschestvo/756844/> (In Russ.).

² Federal target program "Development of domestic and inbound tourism in the Russian Federation (2011-2018)". URL: <https://tourism.gov.ru/contents/deyatelnost/programmy-i-proekty/gosudarstvennye-programmy-realizovannye-rosturizmom-do-2020-goda/federalnaya-tselevaya-programma-razviti-vnutrennego-i-vezdnogo-turizma-v-rossiyskoy-federatsii-2011-2018-gody/>

industry [4].

Meanwhile L. Stach presents a case study of the Project Riese building complexes in the Owl Mountains, Poland to reveal an important problem which is the conflict between the development of commercial and recreational tourism services and the need to protect the environment and cultural heritage [5].

E. Ramos, M. Salgado, R. Saraiva, I. Ramos investigate the example of the Alva valley, Portugal in pursuing to coordinate the interests of local population, tourists and the whole tourist industry in general [6]. The importance of such efforts is echoed by K. Günçe and D. Misirlisoy [7], while R. Wyllie examines the case of South Africa to add academic institutions to this equation since, according to his findings, history departments at academic institutions are embracing tourism as another outlet for the inclusion of history in terms of both the content, but more importantly, the research skills that tourism can impart to history [8].

Meanwhile in Russia aspects of military heritage tourism are also researched by various authors very explicitly. Thus from the point of view of education of young generation military heritage tourism was investigated in the works of V. I. Levin [9] who defines it as a certain way of patriotic education, and also in the works of A. I. Rosikhin [10], who describes the role of military history in promoting education for young people.

A.V. Sekerin [11], in turn, considers in detail the features of information and technological support of military heritage tourism, while A.I. Kolesnikova [12] describes the information and analytical system of military heritage tourism support.

It is necessary to mention the publication of G.A. Gomilevskaya [13], in which the military heritage tourism is evaluated from the organizational and economic context, and similarly the work of T.V. Degtyareva [14], where in-detail attention is paid to the organizational and technological aspects.

A.A. Fatueva's article [15] outlines the prospects of development of military heritage festivals in Tula region, and the publications by G.V.

Aleksushin [16] and Y.N. Gaivoronskaya [17] separately consider the role of military heritage reconstruction in the context of military heritage tourism organization.

At the same time, the prospects of military heritage tourism are analyzed in the works of modern domestic scientists mainly at the regional level. Here we can note the works by E.V. Logvina [18] and E.E. Ibragimov [19], where the authors consider the prospects of military heritage tourism in regards to the Republic of Crimea with an attempt to determine its potential. It is also worth noting that the issue of prospects is similarly addressed by A.A. Saburina [20], who analyzes the possibilities of its development in Kaliningrad region, as well as by Z.H. Mukhamedova [21], where the author explores the potential of military heritage tourism in Volgograd region and from this point of view proceeds to assess its prospects.

However, in the current conditions of rapid and continuous adjustment of the tourism sphere to the emerging new operational conditions, the obtained results require renewal and clarification.

Thus, it becomes relevant to analyze the prospects for the development of military heritage tourism in Primorsky Krai as a territorial subject in which the state museum-reserve "Vladivostok Fortress", created in 2019 by the decree of the President of the Russian Federation and by the resolution of the Russian Ministry of Culture, has allowed to accumulate the resources of military heritage tourism.

Methodology

As a result, the goal of the study is to determine the prospects for the development of military heritage tourism within the borders of Primorsky Krai. To fulfill the objective of the work it is necessary to consider the following problems:

- to systematize the current development of military heritage historical tourism in Primorsky Krai;
- to determine the resource base of military-historical tourism in the Primorsky territory and to specify it;
- to analyze the supply side of military heritage tourism;

- to highlight and systematize the prospects for the development of military heritage tourism in Primorsky Krai.

Research methods include the following: method of analysis, comparison, induction, deduction.

Results

In Primorsky Krai military heritage tourism is

considered to be one of the important directions of development of the regional tourist product. Data from Tourist Information Centre of Primorsky Krai reveals the fact that almost 8% of all the developed local tour itineraries to certain extent exploit the theme of military heritage [22]. Consumers' interest in this regard can be explained by numerous factors presented in the figure.

Fig. 1 – Factors for the development of military-historical tourism in Primorsky Krai

At the same time, the most popular objects of military-historical routes are medieval settlements (in Krasny Yar, Yekaterinovka) – (26%), 13% include a visit to the Izumrudnaya Dolina (Emerald Valley) Park in the Ussuri urban district, while 52% of the routes include Vladivostok Fortress objects [13].

Vladivostok Fortress is a special fortification object, which is a complex of long-term defensive constructions built in the late XIX – early XX century in Vladivostok and its immediate surroundings [23].

In its peculiarity, the Vladivostok Fortress is an object that is unique in many respects. First of all, its defensive construction was the most powerful and advanced fortification complex not only

within the country (at that time it was the Russian Empire) but in the whole world. The Vladivostok Fortress is not one particular building – it is the overlarge military and historical structure, which, according to the museum-reserve 'Vladivostok Fortress', includes over eight hundred objects, Among them are defensive structures (forts, strong points, redoubts, coastal and land batteries, powder cellars, anti-submersible caponiers and half-caponiers), infrastructure facilities (administration buildings, barracks, outhouses, warehouses, food storages, sparking radio stations, etc.), communications (roads, bridges and catacombs), communications (cableway network, berths)^{3,4}

In general, the construction of the

³ Objects of the Vladivostok fortress. URL: <http://kfss.ru/object/obekty-vladivostokskoy-kreposti/vladivostokskaya-krepost>

⁴ Information from the Unified State Register of Cultural Heritage Objects (Historical and Cultural Monuments) of the Peoples

Vladivostok Fortress is one of the most interesting pages of fortification history that influenced not only the Russian Empire, but the world as a whole, because the fortress is an outstanding example of how a defensive complex in different eras could keep safety not only on land borders, but sea borders as well against different opponents.

Among the forts available for tourist display there are Fort Pospelov, Fort No.1, Fort No.7, Fort No.12. It should be separately noted that all the listed objects are objects of cultural heritage of federal significance according to the Russian

cultural heritage register. Besides, according to the Register, among of all subjects of the Russian Federation, Primorsky Krai has the maximum number of entries of objects of federal significance, including such fortification objects as forts, batteries, redoubts and caponiers (total of 63 objects) [30]. It is worth noting that the Vladivostok Fortress is already a very popular and well-known military heritage object in Primorsky Krai, as can be seen from the number of offered excursions which cover almost the entire complex of the fortress as is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – The main excursions to the Vladivostok Fortress ^{5,6}

Organiser	Excursion	Object	Duration	Cost (as of 24.01.2022)
Vladivostok Fortress Museum-Reserve	A tour of the dungeons of Fort 1	Fort №1 named after Mikhail Fedorovich	2 hours	Full price 600 roubles
	Evening Fort №1			
	Secrets of Fort №7	Fort №7 named after Tsesarevich Alexey		
	Butterfly Fort	Fort №12 named after Vladimir Saint	2 hours excluding road	Full price 400 roubles
	Mists are born here	Grand Ducal Battery and coastal caponier at Akhlestyshv cape	3 hours	Full price 800 roubles
Vladivostok Diggers Club	Fort №7	Fort №4 named after Emperor Alexander I	5 hours	1300 roubles / person
	Secret paths of the party	Special object №1 of the Ministry of Defence of Vladivostok and the shelter of the Directorate of National Security and Internal Affairs	2 hours	1050 roubles / person
	Russian Island: the Far Frontier	Fort of Rurik, Fort №10 of Oleg, coastal battery №982	6 hours	1700 roubles / person
	Fort №3	Fort №3 named after Catherine the Great	4 hours	1400 roubles / person

The table shows that practically all the forts accessible to the public are used as sightseeing objects. The only exceptions are those which are not accessible or are difficult to access from a transport point of view.

Similarly, it is worth noting that overnight military heritage tours are also available on the market (Table 2).

As a result, it can be noted that today the Vladivostok Fortress is a promising object of military-historical tourism, despite some significant

difficulties. First and foremost, the main problem of the fortress is its destruction: the maritime climate, the constant salt winds and ruthless vandalism have not passed over the fortress objects, many of which have had to be recognized as ruined.

The location of the fortress should not be overlooked: most of the forts occupy the dominant peaks, which makes access to them difficult. Transport accessibility in this case becomes considerably limited due to the poor state of roads or

of the Russian Federation. URL: <https://opendata.mkrf.ru/opendata/>

⁵ Excursions of the Vladivostok Fortress Museum-Reserve. URL: <https://fortressvl.ru/tours/>

⁶ Excursions of the Vladivostok digger Club. URL: <http://www.vladdig.org/>

their absence altogether. At the same time, the trails running through the forested terrain, overgrown with tough brush, are often the only route option, similarly reducing the means of mass attendance. It is worth noting that some of the buildings themselves are also considered quite dangerous, especially their underground parts – stairs, wells, rafters, flooded and ruined areas – so as a tourist attraction they are aimed mainly at the conscious, middle-aged visitors.

As a result, on the example of the Vladivostok fortress objects it is possible to identify and specify in detail the main problems hindering the successful development of military heritage tourism in Primorsky Krai, as well as to determine the measures needed to level out their negative effect.

Table 2 – Military heritage overnight tours to Primorsky Krai

<i>Title</i>	<i>Organiser</i>	<i>Days</i>	<i>Cost</i>
Military Historical Excursion and Automotive History Museum	Dalinfotur	3	7 800
Introducing Vladivostok	Far Eastern Centre for Tourism	2	8700
Vladivostok is a Military City, a City of the Sea!	Vostokintour	3	10 150
Vladivostok	Putivochka	5	14200
Russia, Vladivostok	Travel market	5	15200
The four stories of Vladivostok	Big Country	4	46 800
Vladivostok – a fortress city	Nissa Tour	5	64 665

Table 3 – Measures to further develop military heritage tourism in Primorsky Krai

<i>Problem</i>	<i>Measure</i>	<i>Effect</i>
Inaccessibility of objects (Fort No.3, Fort No.5)	Development of transport infrastructure, special passable transport options.	Reduction of transport costs; Ability to form a safer product
Destruction of facilities (Suvorov`s fort)	Partial possible restoration of facilities	Increase of market offer
Dangerous objects (Grand-Ducal Battery, Fort No.7, Fort No.12, Novosiltsevskaya Battery)	Installation of fencing, special warning signs, introduction of visitor safety monitoring systems	Increase in number of tourists Increase in coverage of the target audience

At the same time, in addition to excursion routes for military heritage tourism, the resource base is also beginning to be actively used for holding various festivals in the region.

It is worth noting that the organization of festivals involving heritage sites is a rather promising process in relation to Primorsky Krai, which shows positive dynamics of attracting audiences, which in turn allows the active development of military heritage tourism. For instance, the Vladivostok Fortress facilities are currently used as thematic festival locations organized by the museum-reserve.

It should be mentioned that the number of such events is increasing: for example, from 2013 to 2018 the annual festival 'Vladivostok Fortress' was held, from 2019 the project 'Music Picnic' was implemented, in 2021 – the festival 'Fortress Day' was introduced. However, according to the museum-reserve, there are plans to increase the

number of such events in subsequent years, involving more venues. Nevertheless, the Musical Picnic festival, which has been held annually since 2019 at Fort Pospelov, can currently be considered a successful project that has helped to popularize the fortress and to attract large audience. It is worth noting that in 2020 the festival was located at three sites of the fortress at once, namely the aforementioned Pospelov Fort, Fort No.1 and Powder Cellar No.13. According to data from the Vladivostok Fortress Museum-Reserve, 3,000 people attended the festival in 2019. In 2020, despite the unstable situation caused by the pandemic, 5,000 people attended the festival. However, in 2021, their number dropped to 450 people – the festival was not organized on a full scale due to bad weather.

Similarly, the not so long ago established festival 'Fortress's Day', held on the Fort 1 territory and attended by almost 3,000 people, can be

considered a way to popularize the Vladivostok fortress and military heritage tourism in general. In the framework of this event, the program of which was devoted to Baron Budberg, who was the head of the fortress' headquarters for 11 years, educational meetings, historical lectures highlighting history of the Vladivostok fortification, interactive zones and play areas for children were arranged to introduce them to the military heritage objects and historical personalities, in any form connected with the fortress' history.

Conclusion

Thus, in the course of the study, it was verified that military heritage tourism is a well-established direction of regional development that implements certain functions that are in demand in modern society, including cultural-historical function and educational function.

The resource base was streamlined. Study shows that it includes rich historical heritage in its core, which is framed by the availability of places of interest (of all subjects of the Russian Federation, Primorsky Territory has the maximum number of fortification objects of federal significance in the he Russian cultural heritage register), an event component and the surrounding information environment.

The analysis of the available regional routes

aimed at the acquaintance of general public with the military heritage, revealed the wide majority of them are focused around the Vladivostok fortress.

In the course of the study, an analysis of the military-heritage themed excursions and overnight tours was also carried out, a comprehensive author's register of display objects was compiled, recording their current state and relevance of the objects. Special attention was paid to the event component of military heritage tourism. Measures were proposed for the further development of military heritage tourism in Primorsky Krai, the implementation of which will further reduce transport costs, create an opportunity to form a safer product, expand the market offer and the target audience.

Further discussion

The issues of military heritage tourism are relevant for scientific discussion in modern conditions. At the same time, the theoretical results obtained in the framework of this study should be verified in the course of the medium- and long-term analysis. Meanwhile, a more detailed projection of the obtained results for other territorial subjects of the Russian Federation will help to build a more universal theoretical framework for the development of military heritage tourism.

References

1. Elliot, A., & Milne, D. (2018). War, Tourism and modern Japan. *Japan Review International Research Centre for Japanese Studies, National Institute for the Humanities*, 33, 3-28.
2. Driessen, S. (2019). The significance of battlefield tours for the Dutch military. In: *Cristal Military Studies*. Erasmus School of History, Culture and Communication, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Rotterdam, 1-19. doi: 10.1080/23337486.2019.1651044.
3. Foulk, D. (2016). The impact of the "economy of history": The example of battlefield tourism in France. *Mondes du Tourisme*, 1-22. doi: 10.4000/tourisme.1338.
4. Zienkiewicz, A., Podciborski, T., & Kaźmierczak, R. (2021). Increased interest in military tourism on selected examples from the area of northern and northeastern Poland. *Travel and Tourism Studies in Transport Development Communications*, 4, 38-50. doi: 10.26552.
5. Stach, L. (2014). The Development of Tourism at Military-Historical Structures and Sites – A Case Study of the Building Complexes of Project Riese in the Owl Mountains. *Polish Journal of Sport and Tourism*, 21(1), 36-41. doi: 10.2478/pjst-2014-0005.
6. Ramos, E., & Salgado, M., Saraiva, R., & Ramos, I. (2019). Importance of Historical Recreations in Military Tourism: Lusitanos Resistance to the Roman Invasion in Serra da Estrela. In: *7th International Conference on Tourism & Hospitality Management*, 136-146.
7. Günçe, K., & Misirlisoy, D. (2014). Adaptive reuse of military establishments as museums:

- conservation vs. museography. *Defence Sites. WIT Transactions on The Built Environment*, 143, 125-136. doi: 10.2495/DSHF140111.
8. Wyllie, R. (2014). "Entrenching nostalgia": The historical significance of battlefields for South African tourism. *Historia*, 59(2), 210-228.
 9. Levin, V. I. (2017). Voенно-istoricheskij turizm kak odin iz sposobov patrioticheskogo vospitaniya [Military heritage tourism as one of the ways of patriotic education]. *Nauka i kul'tura Rossii [Science and Culture of Russia]*, 1, 364-365. (In Russ.).
 10. Rossikhin, A. I., & Khamnaeva, N. I. (2020). Rol' voенно-istoricheskogo turizma v patrioticheskom vospitanii podrastayushchego pokoleniya [The role of military heritage tourism in the patriotic education of the younger generation]. In: *Sotsial'nye i gumanitarnye nauki. Yurisprudenciya [Social sciences and humanities. Jurisprudence]: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of the national scientific-practical conference «Education and science»*. Ulan-Ude: East Siberian State University of Technology and Management, 101-104. (In Russ.).
 11. Sekerin, A. V. (2017). Informacionno-tekhnologicheskoe obespechenie voенно-istoricheskogo turizma v Kurskoj oblasti. [Information and technological support of military heritage tourism in the Kursk region]. In: *Aktual'nye problemy razvitiya turisticheskoy infrastruktury [Actual problems of tourism infrastructure development]: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of the scientific-practical conference*. Kursk: LLC "Investsphere", 28-32. (In Russ.).
 12. Kolesnikova, A. I., & Zakharova, O. A. (2020). Informacionno-analiticheskaya sistema podderzhki voенно-istoricheskogo turizma [Information and analytical system for support of military heritage tourism]. In: *Aktual'nye problemy nauki i tekhniki [Actual problems of science and technology]: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of the national scientific-practical conference*. Rostov-on-Don: Don State Technical University, 897-899. (In Russ.).
 13. Gomilevskaja, G. A. (2019). Organizacionno-ekonomicheskie aspekty voенно-istoricheskogo turizma v Primorskom krae [Organizational and economic aspects of military heritage tourism in Primorsky Krai]. *Territoriya novyh vozmozhnostej. Vestnik Vladivostokskogo gos. un-ta ekonomiki i servisa [The territory of new opportunities. Bulletin of the Vladivostok State University of Economics and Service]*, 2(41), 55-72. doi: 10.24866/VVSU/2073-3984/2018-2/055-072. (In Russ.).
 14. Degtyareva, T. V. (2019). Organizacionno-tekhnologicheskie aspekty razvitiya voенно-istoricheskogo turizma [Organizational and technological aspects of the development of military heritage tourism]. *International innovation research: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of XIX International scientific-practical conference*. Penza: Science & Education, 111-115. (In Russ.).
 15. Fatueva, A. A., & Promyslova, K. S. (2019). Razvitie sobytijnogo turizma v tul'skoj oblasti: voенно-istoricheskie festivali [Development of event tourism in the Tula region: military heritage festivals]. In: *Fizicheskaya kul'tura, sport i zdorov'e studencheskoj molodezhi: problemy i perspektivy razvitiya [Physical culture, sports and health of students: problems and prospects of development]: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of the XIV International scientific-practical conference*. Tula: TulSU, 677-683. (In Russ.).
 16. Aleksushin, G. V., & Bezruchenkov, A. Yu. (2020). Voенно-istoricheskaya rekonstrukciya – element voенно-istoricheskogo turizma i eyo vliyanie na turizm v Samarskoj oblasti [Military heritage reconstruction is an element of military-historical tourism and its impact on tourism in the Samara region]. In: *Ekonomika predpriyatij, regionov, stran: aktual'nye voprosy i sovremennye aspekty [Economy of enterprises, regions, countries: current issues and modern aspects]: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of the II International scientific-practical conference*. Penza: Science & Education, 125-128. (In Russ.).
 17. Gajvoronskaja, Yu. N. (2018). Rekonstrukciya kak forma izucheniya istoricheskikh sobytij [Reconstruction as a form of studying historical events]. *Organizaciya raboty s molodezh'yu [Organization of work with young people]*, 2, 7. (In Russ.).
 18. Logvina, E. V. (2021). Voенно-istoricheskij turizm – odno iz perspektivnykh napravlenij turizma v

- Krymu [Military heritage tourism is one of the promising areas of tourism in the Crimea]. In: *Nashchee i budushchee Rossii v menyayushchemsya mire: obshchestvenno-geograficheskii analiz i prognoz [The present and future of Russia in a changing world: socio-geographical analysis and forecast]*: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of the international scientific conference, 857-862. (In Russ.).
19. Ibragimov, E. E., & Avdil', I. E. (2019). Perspektivy razvitiya voenno-istoricheskogo turizma v Krymu [Prospects for the development of military-historical tourism in the Crimea]. In: *Prioritetnye napravleniya i problemy razvitiya vnutrennego i mezhdunarodnogo turizma v Rossii [Priority directions and problems of development of domestic and international tourism in Russia]*: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of the II All-Russian with international participation scientific-practical conference. Bakhchisarai: Arial, 174-178. (In Russ.).
20. Saburina, A. A. (2021). Strategicheskoe videnie razvitiya voenno-istoricheskogo turizma na territorii Kaliningradskoi oblasti [Strategic vision of the development of military-historical tourism in the Kaliningrad region]. In: *Sovremennyye problemy razvitiya industrii turizma i gostepriimstva [Modern problems of tourism and hospitality industry development]*: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of the II interregional scientific and practical conference-discussions. Vologda: Vologda State Un-ty, 75-78.
21. Mukhamedova, Z. Kh., & Mandrik, E. L. (2019). Perspektivy razvitiya voenno-istoricheskogo turizma v gorode Volgograd [Prospects for the development of military-historical tourism in the city of Volgograd]. In: *Prioritetnye napravleniya i problemy razvitiya vnutrennego i mezhdunarodnogo turizma v Rossii [Priority directions and problems of development of domestic and international tourism in Russia]*: The Collection of scientific articles based on the materials of the II All-Russian with international participation scientific-practical conference. Bakhchisarai: Arial, 284-287. (In Russ.).
22. Shchur, V. V., Sergienko, Yu. Yu., & Kononov, A. Yu. (2020). Organizational and Economic Aspects of Military Heritage Tourism in Primorsky Krai. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*. Atlantis Press, 3203-3208. doi: 10.2991/aebmr.k.200312.462.
23. Avilov, R. C., Ayushkin, N. B., & Kalinin, V. I. (2016). *Vladivostokskaya krepost'. Chast' 3. Krepost' trekh izmerenij [Vladivostok fortress. Part 3. Fortress of three dimensions]*. Vladivostok: Dalnauka. (In Russ.).